

The Role of the Pharmaceutical Facility Manager in Conflict Management

Nemsitsveridze Nino ¹

Gorgaslidze Nana ²

Zarqua Tea ³

Nikuradze Nestani ⁴

Dughashvili Nanuli ⁵

Kvizhinadze Natia ⁶

Abstract

It is well known and on the based literary sources were known that one of the important statements of interpersonal communication is the study conflicts. In pharmacy institutions in various facilities, which is suggested by the dissatisfaction of the users of the pharmaceutical product, as well as the high price of the drug, or its incorrect non-targeted use. In the recent study used a questionnaire and interviewers were pharmacists, who provides Important date and information about conflicts of interest. Based on the statistical analyses of the questionnaire data, it was found that the manager's role in resolving conflicts is important, as well as the manager's knowledge and skills to manage the conflict situation, both in terms of customer relations and teamwork. Based on the above, more attention should be paid to retraining of managers and pharmacists from the point of view of raising awareness and resolving conflict situations with consumers. The manager should pay more attention to the issues of employee motivation, which will help increase labour productivity and reduce punitive measures. In pharmacies, there are problems with the labour code, and the manager or his superiors must resolve the terms of the employer's contract.

Keywords: Pharmacist, pharmacy, conflicts, consumer.

^{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6} Department of Social and Clinical Pharmacy of Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Introduction: One of the important places in interpersonal communication is the study of conflict. Unfortunately, there is a certain kind of conflict in the collective of any organization [4]. Even pharmacy

institutions are not immune from such situations [5,6] The literature describes examples of conflicting cases in pharmacy practice, related to customer dissatisfaction with the proposed product, as well as the high price of the drug, or its incorrect or non-targeted use [1,2,3,7].

The aim of the study is to reveal the types of conflicts in pharmaceutical institutions and to develop recommendations for their solution.

First of all, we considered it necessary to prepare a questionnaire that allowed us to obtain the necessary information as a result of an online survey of pharmacists. Stages of the research:

- ✓ At the next stage, the obtained results were analyzed;
- ✓ Based on the received data, we formed conclusions;
- ✓ Recommendations were developed.

A closed-ended, questionnaire-based online survey was conducted. The questionnaire was developed using Google Forms. The survey was completely anonymous, therefore it was a guarantee of honest answers from the respondents.

Results: We interviewed a total of 34 pharmacists and representatives of pharmaceutical companies based in Georgia: Aversi, PSP, Pharmadepot, and Farm House.

As a result of the research, it was revealed that the most conflict situations in pharmacies are recorded between the customer and the pharmacy staff. The majority (97%) noted the conflict between the user and the pharmacist, and only one respondent noted the conflict situation between the employees and the manager, as for the employees in the collective, the respondents did not note it. One of the respondents, after filling out the questionnaire, said that in his practice he never noticed a conflict between employees. According to the results of the mentioned survey, the initiator of the conflict is most often the consumer. In this case, we should draw attention to the fact that the target group of the mentioned research was represented only by pharmacists, respectively

We can have a subjective opinion on this question because only one side of the conflict evaluates the situation. That is why the mentioned result showed

The a need to continue research to know the position of the other side of the conflict, the consumers.

Diagram 1.

When asked who resolves conflicts most often, the majority named the manager 65% (22), although 32% (11) of the interviewees believe that the resolution of conflicts is most often done by ordinary pharmacists. One respondent nominates the customer as the conflict resolver. As we have already mentioned, the overwhelming majority of respondents named the user as the source of the conflict, it is interesting what is named as the cause of dissatisfaction most often. The opinions of the respondents were divided, 9 of them named the bad mood of the user as the cause of the conflict, while 25 named the price of the medicines. Low quality of medicine and poor service were not observed. When talking about conflicts between employees, the majority of respondents (32 people) note that conflicts between employees in their work environment are not frequent. Based on the research results, we can say that this does not rule out their absence.

We asked if the managers of the pharmacy fired or transferred the employee who initiated the conflict, the majority of the respondents (25 respondents) gave a negative answer to this question, and 9 of them confirmed the existence of a similar case. Only one respondent refrained from answering (**diagram 2**).

When asked whether there were any conflict situations between the pharmacy team and the managers of the chain, and if so, what kind of punitive measures were implemented, the majority of respondents (29) stated that such conflicts did not occur. The practice of 5 of them remembers such cases. Punitive measures were not implemented. And 5 respondents stated that in similar cases such methods as monetary fines or dismissal of the employee were used. We also touched on the issue of discipline. According to 30 respondents, sanctions in case of discipline violation are in most cases verbal warning/reprimand, sometimes loss of salary.

In the survey, no facts of dismissal due to disciplinary violation were recorded. As for the breach of the conditions stipulated by the Labor Code on the part of the employer, 47% (16) of the interviewees have not encountered similar situations, while 53% (18) report overtime working hours without additional pay. When asked whether they had a conflict regarding salary or distribution of bonuses, the majority of respondents stated that conflicts on similar topics did not occur in their work practice, while 7 respondents did. Accordingly we can assume that conflicts regarding the distribution of salaries or bonuses in pharmacy chains are rare, although the fact proves that they still exist.

In conclusion, we can say about the importance of the manager's role in resolving conflicts, all managers should have the knowledge and skills to manage a conflict situation, both about customers and in the collective. For this, more attention should be paid to the training of managers and pharmacists on raising

awareness and the rules for dealing with conflict situations with consumers; It is desirable to have a transparent system of distribution of premiums; the manager should pay more attention to the issues of employee motivation, which will help increase labor productivity and reduce the punitive measure. In pharmacies, there are problems related to the labor code, and the manager or his superiors must resolve them by the terms of the employer's contract.

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